

**Use of shift work in globally distributed software development - Sri Lankan IT
professionals' perspective**

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Purpose- To explore information technology (IT) professionals' perception towards shift-based work pattern used by globally distributed software development (GDSD) firms in Sri Lanka in terms of the effects of shift work on them and strategies they used to cope with shift work.

Design/methodology/approach- A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. Descriptive statistics and factor analysis were used for data analysis.

Findings- The findings led to identify the characteristics of shift work environment, benefits and drawbacks of shift work for IT professionals, strategies used by IT professionals to cope with shift work, and their overall evaluation of the shift work environment.

Research limitations/implications- The results of the questionnaire survey provided access to breadth of experience. If qualitative data were also obtained those could have been provided depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

Practical implications- The findings of the study suggest that shift work creates problems for IT professionals' health that call for improvements in the areas that are deleterious while retaining or enhancing those that are beneficial for the shift-based workforce.

Social implications- An understanding of the consequences of shift work for the rhythm of minds and bodies, families and social lives and the routines of rest of the community, and ways to cope with shift work may help the industry to flourish at large.

Originality/value- Minimal literature has been found specific to the cohort of IT professionals full-time engaged in GDSD on shift-basis with respect to their view of it and issues related to their employment arrangement. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide insight into benefits, challenges and issues associated with shift work to allow individuals and organizational leaders to better understand and utilize shift-based work pattern in GDSD. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Keywords: Globally distributed software development, IT professionals, Information technology, Shift work, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Shift work describes a contextual factor related to work pattern (Chan and Jepsen, 2009).

Traditionally, much of the workforce works within the temporal bounds of the traditional workday (e.g 9.00 am to 5.00 pm) (Root and Wooten, 2008). However, some categories of

workers such as police officers and nurses are well recognized to work in alternative shifts (Beers, 2010; Greenberg, 2006). Yet, recent literature increasingly provides evidence that information technology (IT) professionals engaged in globally distributed software development (GDSD) collaboratively work on the same development project with the aid of information and communication technologies (King and Torkzadeh, 2008; Sarker and Sahay, 2004; Sarker and Sarker, 2009). Although software development, it self, is identified to be complex, time-consuming and often stressful many software development firms recognize GDSD as an important avenue to gain competitive advantage (e.g., Carmel and Agarwal, 2001; Sarker et al., 2010).

The term "shift work" is referred to work schedules in which workers "shift" their schedules on some regular basis from daytime to evening or nighttime (Beers, 2010; Finn, 1981). Although shift work has become popular as an alternative work arrangement, most previous research (e.g. Wickramasinghe, 2010) used people employed full-time on regular stable work hours excluding people employed full-time on alternative shifts that range from, for instance, 17 hour or 24 hour time span. Further, our review of literature on shift work to date has been able to locate several studies pertaining to areas such as effective allocation of workers to specific shifts (e.g. Al-Yakoob and Sherali, 2008) and the influence of shift work practices to organizations in terms of financial benefits, costs, and risks associated with such a venture (Jirjahn, 2008; King and Torkzadeh, 2008; Kotlarsky and Oshri, 2005; Sakthivel, 2007). A few studies that investigated the influence of shift work on employees suggest that shift work causes physical and psychological strain for many workers (e.g. Chan and Jepsen, 2009; Haines III et al., 2008; Sarker et al., 2010), and shift workers perceive their work environment less favourably than comparable day workers (Chan and Jepsen, 2009).

Globally distributed software development is referred to collaborative software development internationally with employees from multiple locations are getting involved (Carmel and Agarwal, 2001). The literature identifies time and space differences as key

challenges in GDSD (e.g., Carmel, 1999) and emphasizes the importance of effective communication, coordination, and control for the success of GDSD (e.g., Carmel and Agarwal, 2001). For instance, in the context of GDSD, Sarker et al. (2010, p. 211) state “selected employees at one centre are expected to regularly coordinate their activities (and collaborate) with employees at the overseas centres. Significant time differences between these centres mandate the need for employees in one (or both) location(s) to stretch their work times, and thus create conflicts with their family time”. Therefore, distributed work could bring in its own set of frustrations due to the nature of work hours. Sri Lankan IT professionals involved in GDSD for client firms located in the USA, the EU and the Asia-Pacific region. The literature provides evidence that working time is of considerable importance to IT professionals attached to offshore software development in Sri Lanka (e.g., Wickramasinghe, 2010). However, these studies (e.g., Wickramasinghe, 2010) investigated the work context of regular day workers. Hence, minimal literature has been found specific to the cohort of IT professionals full-time engaged in GDSD on shift-basis with respect to their view of it and issues related to their employment arrangement. Notwithstanding the financial and service capability advantages to firms in moving to shift-based work pattern it is important to investigate employees’ perception towards shift-based work environment within which they operate. In this regard, Niederman et al. (2006, p. 57) emphasize the need of investigating working conditions of employees engaged in GDSD. This becomes vital as project outcomes are often judged based on time-related measures and to make projects successful IT professionals are working or routinely available round the clock in the GDSD (King and Torkzadeh, 2008; Sarker and Sarker, 2009).

In the above context, the main objective of this study is to explore IT professionals’ perception towards shift-based work pattern used by GDSD firms in Sri Lanka. The study specifically explored a) effects of shift work on IT professionals, and b) strategies they used to cope with shift work. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide insight into benefits, challenges and issues associated with shift work to allow individuals and organizational

leaders to better understand and utilize shift-based work pattern in GDSD. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. In order to provide context for this article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background

Shift work

The literature identifies shift work as a form of work scheduling in which employees succeed each other at the same workstation in shifts often outside the normal work hours on a regular basis as directed by the workplace (Boggild and Knutsson, 1999; Rosa and Colligan, 1997; Wilson, 2002). There can be several shift design alternatives (Oexman et al., 2002). For instance, organizations use three shifts per day, which are named as day shift (first shift), evening shift (second shift), and night shift (third shift). The day shift is the work period in which half or more of the hours fall between 8am to 4pm; the evening shift is the work period that is scheduled to end at or near midnight, the night shift is the work period that is scheduled to start at or near midnight. Organizations that use several shifts to cover a particular working day can organize shift schedules in a rotating pattern, where rosters frequently change between day, evening and night (Oexman et al., 2002; Rosa and Colligan, 1997). Alternatively, organizations can use fixed shift schedules, where working hours and working days do not rotate from week to week. In this regard, the literature suggests that shift work schedules may differ markedly in terms of organization, timing and the duration of each shift as well as the speed of rotation of the shifts (Berger and Hobbs, 2006; Fullick et al., 2009; Rosa and Colligan, 1997).

Although, the nature of shift patterns experienced by employees, in general, is widely available in the literature, the nature of shift patterns used in GDSD is not widely available. In a

similar vein, the influence of shift work on IT professionals engaged in GDSD is not widely available although the effect of shift work on employees, in general, is well noted in the literature.

Effects of shift work on employees

The literature suggests that whilst there are benefits of shift work for employees, it has also been associated with several negative effects on employees in comparison to traditional working day. With regard to the benefits of shift work for employees, Finn (1981) suggests that evening or night shift allows employees more free time during the day. In the case of rotating shifts, employees can accumulate several days off in a row on a regular basis. Further, Finn (1981, p. 32) observed that many shift workers have less tension and more relaxed pace on the night shift than during the day because of less supervision and fewer interruptions from clerical and management personnel. Employees who do not prefer to work on a strict timetable and who are comparatively solitary pursuits found to enjoy rotating shifts (Finn, 1981; Harrington, 2001). Further, shift work can be advantageous to a family's financial situation as shift work brings increased wages (Fullick et al., 2009) and allows one parent to be at home with children while the other parent is working. Hence, money is not spent on childcare (Grosswold, 2004). However, some studies (e.g. Finn, 1981) reveal that employees working on evening and night shifts appreciate being able to remove themselves from unwanted family situations or responsibilities.

Many studies suggest that the benefits of shift work must be weighed against its negative effects on health, safety, family and the social life of employees (e.g. Finn, 1981; Fullick et al., 2009; Harrington, 2001; Leka and Jain, 2010). This becomes important as shift work creates dissatisfaction for workers as it puts them out of rhythm with their minds and bodies, families and social lives, and the routines of rest of the community (Admi et al. 2008; Harrington, 2001; Leka and Jain, 2010).

With regard to the negative effects of shift work on health, there is a 24-hour rhythm that governs many of the major biological functions of the human body. For instance, shift work interrupts blood pressure, the cardio-pulmonary system, blood composition, endocrine secretions, appetite, elimination, and the wake-sleep cycle (Finn, 1981; Leka and Jain, 2010; Scott and Judge, 2006). According to Finn (1981, p. 32) the continuous alteration of day and evening, or day, evening, and night work seriously diminishes or entirely precludes adjustment of bodily rhythms. For instance, shift workers suffer from insufficient or poor quality sleep (Finn, 1981; Scott and Judge, 2006). It is suggested that shift workers' attempt to sleep during daytime is often disturbed by excessive and unavoidable light and heat, and by noises from children, housework, telephone calls, and street traffic (Finn, 1981, p. 33). Sleep deprivation, which results from trouble falling asleep, waking during sleep, and waking up early associates with fatigue, anger, stress, and reduced feelings of well-being (Pilcher et al., 1997; Lavidor et al., 2003; Leka and Jain, 2010). Further, employees on shift work may frequently experience common colds and influenza and may be more susceptible to viral and bacterial infections because of the immunological response of the body being weakened by the sleep deprivation (Poissonnet and Veron, 2000; Harrington, 2001; Perkins, 2001). Furthermore, several studies identified appetite and digestion related problems as common for many shift workers (e.g. Atkinson et al., 2008; Boggild and Knutsson, 1999). For instance, Boggild and Knutsson (1999) found significant differences in the changes in meal frequency, composition and the timing of meal intake between shift and day workers in their study. In addition, the loss of appetite and irregular eating habits may lead to weight loss as well as nutritional deficiency (Finn, 1981). In this regard, Reeves et al. (2004, p. 216) suggest that shift workers' chronically impaired health and overall sense of well-being can be linked to the disruption of the natural 24-hour rhythm, changes in physical activity levels and dietary food intake habits.

With regard to the negative effects of shift work on work and workplace, some studies provide evidence that shift work influences employees' speed, reaction time, and the accuracy of

work performance after the evening hours begin and this situation is particularly true for rotating shift workers (Admi et al., 2008; Burgess, 2007). For instance, Admi et al. (2008, p. 251) find difficulties in maintaining adequate levels of work performance when a shift spans night-time hours. Further, Perkins (2001) suggests that several episodes of sleep loss can create a sleep debt which can have noticeable effects on work performance. Previous studies also provide evidence that as little as one night of sleep deprivation impairs complex tasks such as decision-making (e.g., Burgess, 2007; Harrison and Horne, 2000), ability to control one's emotions (e.g., Pilcher and Huffcutt, 1996), decreased motivation (e.g., Totterdell et al., 1994), and difficulties in maintaining performance levels (e.g., Totterdell et al., 1994). In connection to the effect of shift work on capabilities and work performance, Oxtoby (2003) found that night shift workers often miss training events that happen during the day or weekend, and as a consequence they have poorer skills compared to day shift workers. Furthermore, sleep deprivation associated with shift work in conjunction with inadequate recovery periods may influence the ability to maintain alertness during evening or night shifts (Peate, 2007).

With regard to the negative effects of shift work on family life, the literature reveals several disturbances for the family life of shift workers due to the lack of synchrony between their atypical work schedule and family's daily routines (e.g. Haines III et al., 2008; Harrington, 2001; Rosa and Colligan, 1997). For instance, previous studies provide evidence that shift workers are often less able to fulfill their domestic roles (Grosswold, 2004; Harrington, 2001; Wilson, 2002) and often feel isolated from their family (Wilson, 2002). In this regard, the findings of previous studies suggest that shift workers experience difficulties in finding time to spend with their children (Finn, 1981) and as a consequence, the children of shift workers do not succeed as well as children of non-shift workers (Haalebos, 1998; Rosa and Colligan, 1997). Further, Finn (1981) states that "time shift workers spend with their spouses can also be affected by hours of work and ... spouses who wish to spend time with a mate who works during the

evening or night usually have to alter their patterns of sleep, mealtime, and recreation to accommodate the shift worker's atypical schedule” (p. 33).

With regard to the negative effects of shift work on social life, several studies provide evidence that shift workers experience considerable disruption to social activities as their rhythm of working day is different to that of the general population (Finn, 1981; Harrington, 2001; Wilson, 2002). For instance, Finn (1981) reports that shift workers participate in fewer voluntary organizations than daytime workers. Some scholars argue that shift workers may experience dissimilar social lives to those who work a normal dayshift schedule and, as a consequence, they may feel social isolation from their community, and religious and cultural support systems (e.g., Harrington, 2001; Haalebos, 1998). Further, Finn (1981) argued that even if shift workers experience free time, fatigue from poor sleep or the lack of sleep can prevent them from normal social activities. In this regard, the literature suggests that the actual amount of spare time a shift worker has may be equal or even greater than a non-shift worker, yet, positioning and utilizing this spare time may be less favourable (Demerouti et al., 2004, p. 988).

Coping with shift work

The term coping is referred to individuals' behavioural and cognitive efforts to manage situations that are viewed as taxing personal resources (Fullick et al., 2009, p 449). The literature identifies several strategies that can be used by organizations to help shift workers to cope with shift work environment (Bohle and Tilley, 1998; Monk, 2000; Tepas, 1993). For instance, Tepas (1993) suggests that it is within the possibility of many organizations to minimize some of the negative effects of shift work by changing from rotating shifts to fixed shifts. Further, Tepas (1993) and Monk (2000) highlight the importance of shift worker education programmes to help them cope with shift work. Some studies have identified that problems associated with shift work can be reduced in the short term by providing recreational and leisure activities (Fullick et al., 2009; Harrington, 2001). Harrington (2001) and Atkinson et al. (2008) identify the

importance of providing physical fitness facilities to reduce negative effects associated with shift work. Atkinson et al. (2008) state that employees who undertake physical exercise during shift work often cope better with shift work than those who do not take part in physical exercise. In this regard, the literature suggests the importance of effective design and implementation of organization led coping strategies to address issues surrounding shift work (Bohle and Tilley, 1998).

The literature suggests the importance of family and friends of shift workers in coping with negative effects of shift work (Bohle and Tilley, 1998; Tepas, 1993). For instance, Tepas (1993) and Bohle and Tilley (1998) state that it is not only the shift worker has to change his or her behaviour any strategy to cope with shift work should include his or her family members as well. In this regard, Loudon and Bohle (1997) found that support from family and friends enhance both adaptability and tolerance to shift work. Previous studies also provide evidence that shift workers can participate in leisure-time physical activities with their family members not only as a stress-reducing effort but also to overcome the dissatisfaction with the amount of time spent with their families (Nomaguchi and Bianchi 2004).

Some studies provide evidence that the identification of shift worker with their work colleagues and within the team reportedly play a role in shift work tolerance (see Pisarski et al., 2006). It is reported that if a shift worker receive co-worker support, he or she become empowered and confident, experience an increased sense of self-worth, and will have low intention to be absent from work (Pisarski and Bohle, 2001). In this regard, Root and Wooten (2008) identify the support shift workers receive from co-workers and sympathetic supervisors as informal support mechanisms available in the workplace.

According to Root and Wooten (2008), employees may take independent action that interferes with office work that needs to be done, for instance, getting absent without obtaining prior approval (Root and Wooten, 2008). Therefore, Root and Wooten (2008) suggest that coping mechanisms that shift workers can rely on may range from the least disruptive (arranging

time off with a cooperative supervisor) to the highest disruptive (independent actions that interfere with work that needs to be done).

Some previous studies suggest that employees who do not tolerate shift work may increase their intake of caffeine and alcohol (e.g. Caruso 2008). Further, it is suggested that such employees may also take medication to fall asleep, gastrointestinal disorders and bowel problems (e.g. Caruso 2008).

Overall, the literature suggests that the extent to which individuals cope with shift work is heterogeneous (Fullick et al., 2009) and there are no universally good or bad coping processes, merely those that might often be better or worse than others in a particular individual (Lazarus, 1993 as cited in Fullick et al., 2009, p. 449). The literature also suggests that as coping with shift work is a dynamic process strategies used may evolve with time and experience (Fullick et al., 2009).

Importance of studying shift work in IT outsourcing sector

Several previous studies conducted in IT outsourcing sector in South Asia provide evidence that IT professionals experience increased stress in the workplace (e.g. Aziz, 2004; Budhwar et al. 2006) and working time is an important work characteristic (e.g. Perlow, 2001; Sarker et al., 2010; Wickramasinghe, 2010). Further, previous studies provide evidence that IT outsourcing firms have introduced value-added initiatives, such as work schedule flexibility, to strategically enhance the performance of employees (e.g., Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu, 2007). However, these studies investigated IT professionals who work within the temporal bounds of the traditional workday in IT outsourcing sector in Sri Lanka (e.g. Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe, 2010; Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu, 2007; Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera, 2010). Therefore, sample selection criteria of these studies had excluded IT professionals who work in alternative shifts. Wickramasinghe and Kumara (2010) found working hours as an important work characteristic for employees engaged in IT enabled services

sector (ITES), which use shift-based work arrangement. However, on the one hand, ITES employees' main job function does not involve producing IT related output although they use IT services in their day-to-day work (e.g., call centre) whereas IT employees are engaged in producing IT related output as their primary job function (e.g. software developers). On the other hand, Wickramasinghe and Kumara (2010) had not investigated in detail the characteristics of shift work and the influence of shift work on ITES employees as they had used a single item measure to explore ITES employees' perception towards working hours (i.e., "I am uncomfortable with my working hours").

The literature reviewed earlier provides evidence that project outcomes of IT professionals engaged in GDSD often judged based on time-related measures; they work or routinely available round the clock in GDSD work environment (King and Torkzadeh, 2008; Sarker and Sarker, 2009). Further, scholars suggest that shift work causes physical and psychological strain and they may perceive shift-based work environment less favourably than comparable day work (e.g., Sarker et al., 2010).

However, we were unable to find any studies that specifically investigated the characteristics of shift work and influence of shift work on IT professionals full-time engaged in shift-based work environment in IT outsourcing sector in any part of the world. For instance, few studies had investigated globally distributed work arrangement on system development teams (e.g. Sarker and Sahay, 2004; Sarker and Sarker, 2009; Sarker et al., 2010). However, these studies do not explain much about the characteristics of shift work and the influence of shift work in terms of health, safety, family and the social life of IT professionals. Therefore, little is known about IT professionals engaged full-time in shift-based work environment. In this context, the present study was conducted to seek answers to: what are the characteristics of shift work environment in GDSD in Sri Lanka? what are the benefits and drawbacks of shift work for IT professionals? and what are the strategies IT professionals used to cope with shift work?

Methodology

Sample

For the study, an IT professional is defined as a person who is primarily engaged in the creation and provision of IT related output as his or her primary job function as a full-time employee performing his or her work roles on shift-basis in a firm that engaged in GDSD located in Sri Lanka. The study was carried out using a survey-based approach. The preliminary investigations made by the authors led to reveal that comparatively small number of firms engaged in GDSD use shift-based work pattern covering the full working hours of a particular working day in Sri Lanka compared to the total number of firms engaged in GDSD in the country. We have used the list of firms registered under the Software Exporters' Association of Sri Lanka to identify these firms and we isolated eight firms that had shift-based work pattern covering the full working hours of a particular working day. These eight firms were identified as the firms representing the study population. There were a total of 303 IT professionals engaged full-time on shift-based work pattern in these eight firms. These 303 IT professionals were identified as the study population from which sample had to be drawn. 75 was the largest number of IT professionals employed full-time on shift-bases at a particular firm while 10 is the smallest number of IT professionals engaged full-time on shift-bases at a particular firm in 2010. A contact person was identified at each firm. Of the 303 self-administered survey questionnaires distributed covering the total population of the study, a total of 133 usable responses resulted in 44 per cent response rate. Therefore, the sample of this study consisted of 44 per cent of the total study population. Initial analysis revealed that at least five per cent of the total number of IT professionals on shift-basis at each firm had been included in the sample. The demographics of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

Measures and methods of data analysis

The measures were developed based on the preliminary inquiries made during the study and from the previously reviewed related literature. For the purpose of the study, appropriate scale items were developed using guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978). In doing so, first, the domain of the relevant construct was specified. Then, items were developed to map the construct's conceptual definition. All constructs were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. The items were pre-tested on a convenience sample of 10 IT professionals that fitted with the intended sample of the study and revised accordingly.

In analyzing the responses, multivariate analysis of variance was conducted to check whether any group differences exist among the responses from the eight firms for the variables of the study. The results of the Wilks' Lambda statistic revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) among the responses from the eight firms. Descriptive statistics for the variables are shown in Appendix A, B, and C. Cronbach's alpha of each scale was examined and principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al. 2006).

Results

Shift work characteristics

Table 2 shows the characteristics of shift work. 62.7 per cent of the respondents came from firms that provide services covering the 24-hour time span throughout seven days of the week.

19.8 per cent of the respondents report that their firms operate five days per week from 8.00 am to 10.00 pm. 59.5 per cent of the respondents stated that their shifts rotate weekly.

Take in Table 2

Benefits and drawbacks of shift work

Table 3 shows the benefits of shift work for employees. Factor analysis yielded one factor, which explained 59% (58.61) of the variance.

Take in Table 3

Table 4 shows the drawbacks of shift work for employees. The 19 items had a reliability of 0.858. Factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 84% (84.03) of the variance. Of these three factors, Factor 1 was labelled as “Influence on health”, Factor 2 as “influence on capabilities and career development”, and Factor 3 as “Influence on family and social life”.

Take in Table 4

Table 5 shows employees’ overall evaluation of the shift work environment. Mean values suggest that they are willing to accept regular stable work hours (9 am – 5 pm) if the organization offers such to them instead of the shift-based employment. Further, mean values

shown in Table 5 suggest that respondents are not much interested in the shift-based employment.

Take in Table 5

Coping with shift work

Table 6 shows strategies used to cope with shift work. The 20 items had a reliability of 0.823. Factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 52% (52.13) of the variance. Of these four factors, Factor 1 was labelled as “Individual constructive initiatives”, Factor 2 as “Organization formal initiatives”, Factor 3 as “Organization informal initiatives”, and Factor 4 as “Individual destructive initiatives”.

Take in Table 6

Discussion, conclusions and implications

In the GDSD setting, IT professionals located in different parts of the world work collaboratively on the same project. To synchronize activities of the software development between team members, GDSD firms adopt shift-based work structure. Yet, the literature provides little empirical evidence on IT professionals’ perception towards GDSD work environment. This becomes vital as IT professionals have to bridge, overcome, routinely cross and even transcend the time and place division among GDSD team members (see Sarker and Sahay, 2004, p. 3). Drawing upon a random sample of IT professionals full-time employed in software development on a shift-based work pattern in firms that engaged in GDSD located in

Sri Lanka, the study examined the effects of shift work on IT professionals and strategies they used to cope with shift work. The novel character of this research is that it investigated employees' side of the shift-based work pattern that they experience.

It was found that firms adopt different operating hours such as "8.00 am to 10.00 pm across five days per week" and "seven days of the week in the 24-hour time span" (refer to Table 2). Shift work covers different patterns such as "morning and evening shifts covering 14-hour time span" and "morning, evening, and night shifts covering 24-hour time span". 23 per cent of the respondents were in fixed shifts while 77 per cent were in rotating shifts. In this regard, Jamal (1981) suggests that workers on fixed work schedules (high routine-oriented) would be better off than workers on rotating work schedules (low routine-oriented) in terms of mental health, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and social participation. Further, workers on fixed shift schedules are found to be lower on anticipated turnover, absenteeism and tardiness than workers on rotating shift schedules (Jamal, 1981). In the case of rotating shifts, the literature suggests that the forward rotating schedule that begins on the day, which moves to evening and then to night is better than the backward rotating schedule as circadian rhythms of the body is more capable of adapting to the forward rotating schedule than to the backward rotating schedule (see Oexman et al., 2002, p. 152)

With regard to the effects of shift work on IT professionals, several benefits and drawbacks of shift work for them were identified. The main benefit associated with shift work is that IT professionals can get their personal work done during the day time. In terms of drawbacks associated with shift work, IT professionals highly rated the influence of shift work on their sleeping pattern, problem solving capabilities, analytical skills, and on their eating habits (refer to Appendix B). Previous research also provides evidence that shift work influences employees sleeping pattern (e.g. Lavidor et al., 2003), eating habits (e.g. Reeves et al., 2004), and problem solving capabilities (e.g. Harrison and Horne, 2000). IT professionals also report influence of shift work on their family and social life. These findings support the findings of

previous research such as Grosswold (2004) and Fullick et al. (2009). Mean values suggest that IT professionals do not have many opportunities to undergo training events organized by the workplace. In this regard, Oxtoby (2003) reported that night shift workers have poorer skills compared to day shift workers. Further, Oxtoby (2003) suggests that shift workers often miss educational events that happen during the day or weekend. Furthermore, evening and night shift workers have to move to day shifts to receive extra training that they feel as required (Oxtoby, 2003). However, IT professionals do not report many effects to their health by the shift work. This finding does not support the findings of previous research such as Leka and Jain (2010). However, it should be noted that IT industry in Sri Lanka has emerged in the mid 1990s and, in general, IT professionals employed by the industry is young. This situation might have an impact on the above finding. The item measures used to capture benefits and drawbacks of shift work were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. Factor analysis for the drawbacks of shift work yielded three factors which were named as influence on health, influence on capabilities and career development, and influence on family and social life.

With regard to the overall evaluation of shift work, IT professionals reveal their willingness to accept regular stable work hours (e.g. 9 am – 5 pm) if the organization offers such to them instead of the shift-based employment. Further, they have not selected the shift-based employment because they were interested in such an employment. However, they were satisfied with their work performance as a shift worker. In this regard, the literature suggests that employees may not actively seek shift-based employment but may accept shift work schedules as a necessary part of their chosen profession or because no other job option is available (Rosa and Colligan, 1997). Further, Finn (1981, p. 32) reports that shift workers would prefer not to be on a shift-based employment if they had the opportunity to start over again.

With regard to coping with shift work, it was found that IT professionals highly value possibilities they have to mutually interchange shifts with co-workers, and help they receive from team members and superiors in fulfilling work roles as a shift worker (refer to Appendix

C). Previous research also provides evidence that shift work allows employees to build close working associations with others (e.g. Oxtoby, 2003; Pisarski et al., 2006). Further, Root and Wooten (2008) identified the importance of co-workers' emotional support and assistance in coping with shift work and identified supervisors as gatekeepers who play an important role in empowering employees to manage the domains of work and family. These findings suggest the importance of informal support shift workers receive from co-workers and supervisors in helping them to cope with shift work. However, it was found that taking caffeine and alcohol and becoming aggressive are not popular mechanisms sought by IT professionals in Sri Lanka. The item measures used to capture strategies used by IT professionals to cope with shift work shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. Factor analysis yielded four factors which were named as individual constructive initiatives, organization formal initiatives, organization informal initiatives, and individual destructive initiatives.

The findings presented in this paper would be valuable for academics, practitioners, policy makers, and shift workers, themselves, alike. Due to the complexities involved in software development and increasing relevance of GDSD to gain competitive advantage led organizations to operate round the clock by strategizing about "our time" and "their time" and by synchronizing activities of software development. Time-zone differences of team members of GDSD make the relationship between time and software development team process complex, and the literature (e.g. Sarker and Sahay, 2004) suggests that it is deeply embedded in individual, organizational and societal levels. However, it should be noted that there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing human related issues in the context of GDSD in the literature. We have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated the aspects studied in this research to make straight forward comparisons. Therefore, the findings of our study contribute to the literature on offshore outsourcing and GDSD. However, more empirical work is needed to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Yet, we

believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Further, practitioners need valid information to guide their actions in creating suitable work environment. Although GDSD using shift-based work pattern provides unique business opportunity for organizations, the findings of the study suggest that shift work creates problems for IT professionals' health, family life and social activity. Hence, the findings of the study highlight the areas that call for improvements in facilitating IT professionals to maximize the benefits of shift work as well as to minimize the harmful consequences of shift work on them.

Furthermore, it is important for government policymakers to become familiar with the shift work environment within which employees operate and effects shift work has on employees. Such an understanding may help the industry to flourish at large by improving the areas that are deleterious while retaining or enhancing those that are beneficial for the shift-based workforce.

In addition, the findings will provide useful information for shift workers themselves to become familiar with consequences of shift work for the rhythm of their minds and bodies, families and social lives and the routines of rest of the community, and ways to cope with shift work.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

The study relied on self-reported data. Actual data such as health condition of employees and their capabilities were left out due to difficulties in securing those from the participating organizations. The validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. It requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples. Hence, future research in different and large samples and longitudinal studies is necessary that complement questionnaire surveys with interviews. Shift scheduling includes the number of hours of work during a shift, how the shifts are rotated, the speed of rotation, when

breaks are given, etc. Therefore, future research could investigate the influence of these specific aspects of shift work on employees' evaluation of shift-based work environment. Further, future research could incorporate other variables such as rewards received for the effort invested in the job. Although we explored the strategies used to cope with shift work, we have not explored the effectiveness of these strategies in sustaining health and wellbeing. Therefore, future research could incorporate such variables.

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Tables

Table 1: Sample demographics

Age (in years):	
Mean	29.78
Std. Deviation	3.2
Skewness	.66
Kurtosis	1.01
Gender:	
Male	90.2%
Female	9.8%
Marital status:	
Single	46.6%
Married	53.4%
Years of experience as a shift worker in the IT industry:	
Mean	3.58
Std. Deviation	2.00
Skewness	.63
Kurtosis	.04
Total years of experience in the IT industry:	
Mean	5.69
Std. Deviation	2.78
Skewness	.41
Kurtosis	.02
The highest level of education:	
Diploma	10.6%
Bachelor's degree	56.6%
Postgraduate degree	33.8%

Table 2: Shift work characteristics

Working hours of the firm [†] :	
8 to 22 X 5 (five days of the week)	19.8
8 to 22 X 7 (seven days of the week)	5.6
24 X 5	11.9
24 X 7	62.7
Shift work structure used by the firm to cover the working hours of a day in weekdays [†] :	
Morning (8 to 17), Evening (14 to 22), and Over Night (21 to 9)	25.4
Morning (8 to 17), Evening (14 to 22), and Over Night On-call (21 to 9)	18.6
Morning (8 to 17) and Evening (14 to 22)	28.8
Morning (8 to 17), and Evening and Over Night On-call (17 to 8)	18.6
Day (8 to 20) and Night (20 to 8)	5.9
Evening (14 to 22) and Over Night (21 to 9)	2.5
Shift work structure used by the firm to cover the working hours of a day in weekends [†] :	
No weekend rosters	34.6
24 hours On-call	53.1
Morning (8 to 17), Evening (14 to 22), and Over Night (21 to 9)	6.9
Morning (8 to 17), Evening (14 to 22), and Over Night On-call (21 to 9)	1.5
Morning (8 to 17) and Evening (14 to 22)	3.1
Day (8 to 20) and Night (20 to 8)	.8
Shift rotation:	
No such rotation	22.9
Weekly	59.5
Every two weeks	11.5
Monthly	6.1

[†] Sri Lankan Standard Time in 24 hour clock

Table 3: Benefits of shift work

	F1
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to get my personal work done	.915
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to get banking services	.879
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to interact with government offices to get my personal work done	.858
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to continue my higher studies	.669
Working on a shift system has opened career opportunities for me	.506
Explained variation	58.61
Eigenvalue	2.93
Cronbach's alpha	.802
KMO sampling adequacy	.772
Bartlett's Chi-Square	304.11***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 4: Drawbacks of shift work

	F1	F2	F3
	Influence on health	Influence on capabilities and career development	Influence on family and social life
I get frequent headaches since I started to work on shift basis	.862		
My cholesterol level has increased since I started to work on shift basis	.826		
My blood sugar level has affected since I started to work on shift basis	.806		
My blood pressure level has affected since I started to work on shift basis	.805		
I am suffering from gastrointestinal effects since I started to work on shift basis	.782		
I make frequent visits to my general practitioner since I started to work on shift basis	.755		
I feel as if I am suffering from stress since I started to work on shift basis	.746		
Shift work has affected my sleeping pattern	.746		
I am suffering from symptoms such as wheezing, coughing, chest tightness or shortness of breath since I started to work on shift basis	.674		
Shift work has affected my eating habits	.643		
I feel my analytical skills has reduced due to working on shift basis		.876	
I feel my problem solving capabilities has reduced due to working on shift basis		.870	
I feel my capacity to perform has reduced due to working on shift basis		.710	

I miss training events organized by my organization				.779
I have my doubts regarding career development opportunities available for me as a shift worker				.641
I am unable to take part in social events since I started to work on shift basis				.830
I am unable to meet my friends and relatives since I started to work on shift basis				.793
I am unable to fulfil my domestic roles since I started to work on shift basis				.760
Time I spend with my family has reduced since I started to work on shift basis				.616
Explained variation	41.26	23.82		18.95
Eigenvalue	5.36	3.41		2.33
Cronbach's alpha	.823	.756		.798
KMO sampling adequacy		.818		
Bartlett's Chi-Square		818.33***		

Note: *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 5: Overall evaluation of shift work[†]

	Mean	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
I will accept regular stable work hours (9 am – 5 pm) if the organization offers such to me instead of the shift-based employment	3.86	.98	-.64	-.51
I am satisfied with my work performance as a shift worker	3.41	.87	-.63	-.61
I have selected a shift-based employment because I am interested on that type of work	2.53	.98	.38	-.47

[†] Scale: 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree).

Table 6: Coping with shift work

	F1	F2	F2	F4
	Individual constructive initiatives	Organizational formal initiatives	Organizational informal initiatives	Individual destructive initiatives
I plan family outings based on my shift roster	.753			
My family helps me to overcome tension at work	.721			
I plan social events based on my shift roster	.701			
I exercise regularly to reduce tension	.695			
I undertake spiritual/meditation programmes	.646			
I listen to music while I work	.608			
I seek special assistance from counsellors	.602			
I use rest room facilities provided by my workplace		.840		
I get adequate rest time after each shift		.689		
I get sufficient breaks during a particular shift		.651		
I get day offs after overnight shifts		.612		
I can get leave from work if there is such a requirement		.681		
I get support from my superior while working on the shift system			.895	
I get help from my team members while working on the shift system			.863	
I am encouraged to take a break when I feel stressed during a shift			.824	
I chat with friends while I work			.698	
I can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement			.648	
I have started smoking tobacco or my consumption of tobacco has increased since I started to work on shift basis				.861
I let my feelings out by being aggressive since I started to work on shift basis				.850
I have started taking alcohol or my alcohol consumption has increased since I started to work on shift basis				.821
Explained variation	24.51	16.19	11.43	9.87
Eigenvalue	2.81	2.75	2.62	1.16
Cronbach's alpha	.756	.782	.791	.819
KMO sampling adequacy			.618	
Bartlett's Chi-Square			847.29***	

Note: *** $p < 0.001$

Appendix

Appendix A: Descriptive statistics - Benefits of shift work

	Mean	S.D	Skewness	Kurtosis
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to get banking services	3.57	.88	-.86	-.10
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to get my personal work done	3.49	1.03	-.86	-.15
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to interact with government offices to get my personal work done	3.41	1.03	-.90	-.01
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to continue my higher studies	3.03	1.07	-.02	-.84
Working on a shift system has opened career opportunities for me	2.66	1.02	.33	-.37

Appendix B: Descriptive statistics - Drawbacks of shift work

	Mean	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Shift work has affected my sleeping pattern	3.82	.94	-1.02	.91
I feel my problem solving capabilities has reduced due to working on shift basis	3.73	.74	-.96	.80
I feel my analytical skills has reduced due to working on shift basis	3.54	.90	-.56	-.62
Shift work has affected my eating habits	3.50	.98	-.37	-.98
I feel my capacity to perform has reduced due to working on shift basis	3.42	.95	-.35	-1.05
I have my doubts regarding career development opportunities available for me as a shift worker	3.39	.92	.51	-.09
I feel as if I am suffering from stress since I started to work on shift basis	3.36	.94	-.72	-.70
I am unable to take part in social events since I started to work on shift basis	3.26	.98	-.26	-.85
Time I spend with my family has reduced since I started to work on shift basis	3.24	.90	-.62	-.34
I am unable to meet my friends and relatives since I started to work on shift basis	3.21	1.017	-.10	-1.14
I get frequent headaches since I started to work on shift basis	3.16	.93	-.39	-.89
I am suffering from gastrointestinal effects since I started to work on shift basis	3.15	1.03	-.15	-1.12
I am unable to fulfil my domestic roles since I started to work on shift basis	3.12	.75	-.20	-.65

I make frequent visits to my general practitioner since I started to work on shift basis	3.05	.97	.19	-.73
My cholesterol level has increased since I started to work on shift basis	3.03	.94	.04	-.95
I miss training events organized by my organization	3.02	1.15	-.10	-1.26
My blood sugar level has affected since I started to work on shift basis	2.90	.93	.23	-.69
My blood pressure level has affected since I started to work on shift basis	2.75	.95	.55	-.64
I am suffering from symptoms such as wheezing, coughing, chest tightness or shortness of breath since I started to work on shift basis	2.58	.85	.61	.19

Appendix C: Descriptive statistics - coping with shift work

	Mean	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
I can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement	3.85	.84	-1.02	.71
I get help from my team members while working on the shift system	3.81	.84	-.77	.24
I get support from my superior while working on the shift system	3.78	.85	-.66	.12
I chat with friends while I work	3.66	.74	-.82	.40
I plan family outings based on my shift roster	3.66	.80	-1.09	1.26
I listen to music while I work	3.63	.89	-.78	.32
I plan social events based on my shift roster	3.60	.82	-.96	.37
My family helps me to overcome tension at work	3.60	.94	-.82	.10
I get sufficient breaks during a particular shift	3.55	.89	-.90	.35
I get day offs after overnight shifts	3.51	1.26	-.55	-.74
I get adequate rest time after each shift	3.45	1.04	-.76	-.48
I can get leave from work if there is such a requirement	3.39	1.01	-.58	-.66
I exercise regularly to reduce tension	3.24	.91	-.16	-.60
I am encouraged to take a break when I feel stressed during a shift	2.92	1.01	-.02	-.69
I use rest room facilities provided by my workplace	2.89	1.28	-.04	-1.17
I let my feelings out by being aggressive since I started to work on shift basis	2.82	1.09	-.07	-1.16
I undertake spiritual/meditation programmes	2.71	.91	.42	-.57
I seek special assistance from counsellors	2.65	.83	.33	-.87
I have started smocking tobacco or my consumption of tobacco has increased since I started to work on shift basis	2.39	1.07	.54	-.66
I have started taking alcohol or my alcohol consumption has increased since I started to work on shift basis	2.37	1.01	.61	-.28